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OFLOXACIN (ANTI-BACTERIAL DRUG)

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ABSTRACT

Ofloxacin is one of a new generation of fluorinated quinolones structurally related to nalidixic acid. It is orally administrated broad spectrum anti-bacterial & some anaerobes. Moreover ofloxacin achieves high concentration in most tissues and body fluids. The result of clinical trials with ofloxacin have confirmed the potential for use in a wide range of infections, which was indicated by its in vitro anti-bacterial & pharmacokinetics profiles. It has proven effective against a high percentage of infection caused by gram-negative organisms, slightly less effective against gram positive infections, & effective against some anaerobic infections. Ofloxacin is well tolerated & although experience with the drug in clinical practices to date is limited, bacterial resistance does not appear to develop readily. Thus, ofloxacin is an orally active drug which offers a valuable alternative to other broad spectrum anti-bacterial drug. The synthesis of Ofloxacin was carried out in this article. And quinoline-4(1H)-one is the intermediate that was found in this Ofloxacin. There physiochemical properties & characterization of impurity is also described.

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INTRODUCTION

A) Overview of Fluoroquinolones:

The fluoroquinolones are broad spectrum antibiotics with particular activity against gram-negative organisms, especially *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. These agents are well absorbed when given orally. Because tissues and fluids concentration often exceed the serum drug concentration, these antibiotics are particularly useful for certain infection, such as pneumonia. [1, 2] Fluoroquinolones are usually well tolerated, with few side effects. However, they can have serious adverse effects. [3]

B) Quinolone:

A quinolone antibiotic is a member of a large group of broad spectrum bacteriocidals that that shares a bicycle core structure related to substance 4-quinolone.[4] Nearly all quinolones antibiotics in use are fluoroquinolones, which contains a fluorine atom in their chemical structure and are effective against both gram positive & gram negative bacteria.[5,6]

1.Mechanisms of Action:

Fig no: 1- Mechanisms of Action of Quinolone.

Quinolones are chemotherapeutic bactericidal drugs. They interfere with DNA replication by preventing bacterial DNA from unwinding & duplicating.[7] Specifically, they inhibit the ligase activity of the type 2 topoisomerases, DNA gyrase & topoisomerases 4, which cut DNA to introduce supercoiling, while leaving nuclease activity unaffected. With the ligase activity disrupted, these enzymes release DNA with single & double strand breaks that lead to cell death.[8] The majority of quinolone in clinical use are fluoroquinolones, which have a fluorine atom attached to the central ring system, typically at the 6-position or C-7 position. Most of them are named with the "oxacin" suffix. First & second generation are largely active against gram negative bacteria, whereas third & fourth generation quinolones have increased activity against gram positive & anaerobic bacteria.[9] Some quinolone containing aromatic substituents at their C-7 position are highly active against eukaryotic type 2 topoisomerase.[10]

2) Pharmacology:

The basic pharmacophore, or active structure, of the fluoroquinolone class is based upon the quinolone ring system.[11] Various substitutions made to the quinoline ring resulted in the development of numerous fluoroquinolone drug. The addition of fluorine atom at C-6 distinguishes the successive-generation fluoroquinolones from the first-generation quinolones, although examples are known that omit the atom while retaining antibacterial activity.[12]

3) Pharmacokinetics:

Likely aminoglycosides, the quinolones exhibit concentration-dependent bacterial killing. Bactericidal activity becomes more pronounced as the serum drug concentration increase to approximately 30 times the minimum inhibitory concentration(MIC). Elimination half-lives for the quinolone vary from 1.5 to 16 hrs. Therefore, most of these drug are administrated every 12-24hrs.[13]

4) Synthesis of Quinoline:

a) Skraup synthesis:

Fig no: 2-Synthesis of Quinolone.

5) Newly Classification of Quinolone Antibiotics:

Table no: 1 [3, 14,15,16, 17, 18, 19].

Classification	Agents	Antimicrobial spectrum	General clinical indication
First generation	Nalidixic acid (Neg Gram) Cinoxacin (Cinobac)	Gram-negative organisms (but not pseudomonas species)	Uncomplicated urinary tract infections.
Second generation	1) Norfloxacin (Noroxin) 2) Lomefloxacin (Maxaquin) 3) Enoxacin (Floxin) 4) Ofloxacin (Floxin) 5) Ciprofloxacin (Cipro)	Gram-negative organisms (including pseudomonas species), some gram positive organisms (including Staphylococcus aureus but not Steptococcus pneumonia) and some a typical pathogens.	Uncomplicated & complicated urinary tract infection & pyelonephritis, sexually transmitted disease, prostatitis, skin & soft tissue infections.
Third generation	1) Levofloxacin (Levaquin) 2) Sparfloxacin (Zagam) 3) Gatifloxacin (Tequin) 4) Moxifloxacin (Avelox)	Same as for second-generation agents plus expanded gram-positive coverage (penicillin-sensitive & penicillin-resistant S. pneumonie) & expanded activity against a atypical pathoens.	Acute exacerbations of chronic ronchitis, community-acquired pneumonia.
Fourth generation	Trovafloxacin (Trovan)	Same as for third-generation agents plus broad anaerobic coverage	Same as for first, second & third-generation agents.

Table no: 2- Indication for quinolone antibiotics Labeled by the U.S. Food & Drug Administration. [3, 14,15,16,17,18,19 &20].

Indications	Agents
Uncomplicated urinary tract infection	Nalidixic acid (Neg gram), Cinoxacin (Cinobac) Norfloxacin (Noroxin), Ofloxacin (Floxin)
Complicated urinary tract infections & pyelonephritis	Norfloxacin, lomefloxacin, enoxacin, ofloxacin, ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, gatifloxacin
Lower respiratory tract infections	lomefloxacin, ofloxacin, ciprofloxacin, trovafloxacin
Skin & skin structure infections	ofloxacin, ciprofloxacin, trovafloxacin, , levofloxacin
Urethral & cervical gonococcal infections	Norfloxacin, enoxacin, ofloxacin, ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, gatifloxacin
Urethral & cervical chlamydial & gonococcal infections	ofloxacin, trovafloxacin
Bone & joints infections, gram-negative bacterial infections	ciprofloxacin,
Infections diarrhea	ciprofloxacin,
Typhoid fever	ciprofloxacin,
Prostatitis	Norfloxacin, ofloxacin, trovafloxacin
Acute sinusitis	ciprofloxacin, levofloxacin, gatifloxacin, moxifloxacin, trovafloxacin
Acute exacerbations of chronic bronchitis	sparfloxacin, levofloxacin, gatifloxacin, moxifloxacin, trovafloxacin
Community acquired pneumonia	sparfloxacin, levofloxacin, gatifloxacin, moxifloxacin, trovafloxacin
Intra abdominal infections	trovafloxacin
Gynecologic & pelvic infections	trovafloxacin
Nosocomial pneumonia	trovafloxacin

Table no: 3- Distinguished Characteristics of Quinolone Antibiotics [2,19,21,22,23,24,25,26].

Class & agents	Half- life	Route of administration	Dosage adjustment required	Significant adverse effects	Significant drug interactions
First generation					
1) Nalidixic acid	60-90min	Oral	Renal impairment	-	Warfarin
2) Cinoxacin	1.1-2.7 hrs	Oral	Renal impairment	Hypersensitivity	-
Second generation					
1) Norfloxacin	2.3-5.5hrs	Oral	Renal impairment	-	Warfarin,
2) Lomefloxacin	7-8.5hrs	Oral	Renal impairment	Phototoxicity,	Cyclosporine
3) Enoxacin	3.3-7hrs	Oral	Renal or hepatic	headache	-
4) Ofloxacin	5-8hrs	Oral,	impairment	Phototoxicity	Warfarin, ranitidine
5) Ciprofloxacin	3-5.4hrs	intravenous	Renal or hepatic	Insomnia	bismuth, caffeine
		Oral,	impairment	Nausea, vomiting,	Warfarin,
		intravenous	Renal impairment	abdominal pain	Warfarin, theophyllin, caffeine,
Third generation					
1) Levofloxacin	6hrs	Oral,	Renal impairment	Headache, nausea	-
2) Sparfloxacin	21hrs	intravenous	Renal impairment	Phototoxicity	Drugs that prolong the QT intervals,
3) Gatifloxacin	7hrs	Oral	Renal impairment	-	including class 1, antiarrhythmics,
4) Moxifloxacin	12hrs	Oral	Hepatic	QT-interval	phenothiazines
		Oral	impairment	prolongation	Same as sparfloxacin Same as sparfloxacin Morphine, citric acid-sodium citrate
Fourth generation					
1) Trovafloxacin	7.8hrs	Oral	Hepatic impairment	Dizziness, severe hepatotoxicity, candida l vaginitis	-

6) Quinolone Lethality

Quinolones kill bacteria slowly or quickly, depending on their concentrations. At concentrations that are twice the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) value, bacteria are killed after an overnight quinolone treatment; whereas, at concentrations 5–10 times the MIC value, bacteria die after a few hours of quinolone exposure.[27,28] How slow or rapid killing happens is not fully understood. We know that the first stage in quinolone lethality is the binding of the quinolone to a topoisomerase-DNA cleavage complex. Cleavage complexes contain broken DNA that cannot be resealed by the same topoisomerase if the quinolone is present. However, cleavage complexes and their “hidden” DNA breaks are reversible, so there must be additional events that cause bacterial death.[29].

Fig no: 3- Model of quinolone lethality. (1) Quinolones stabilise the topoisomerase-DNA cleavage complex in which there is a double-strand break. (2) If the cleavage complex is not resolved, (3) replication and transcription cannot happen, which causes slow bacterial cell death. (4) If the topoisomerase is removed, the double-strand break is free, and if left unrepaired, (5) it leads to the fragmentation of the chromosome, which causes rapid bacterial cell death. (6) The stabilised cleavage complex, or the removal of the topoisomerase from the cleavage complex, might lead to the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can cause rapid bacterial cell death.

7) Resistance of Quinolone: [30, 31]

Fig no: 4- Contributions of quinolones to antibiotic resistance. Quinolones can select for quinolone resistance, which is caused by the upregulation of efflux pumps, mutations in DNA gyrase or DNA topoisomerase IV genes or plasmid-encoded resistance genes. Quinolones can also induce resistance to quinolones and non-quinolones antibiotics, presumably by the activation of a stress response that then increases the mutation, recombination or persister formation rates.

8) Adverse effects of Quinolone:

Fluoroquinolones are generally very safe antibiotics which do not cause serious or life-threatening adverse reactions. The most frequent side-effects are gastrointestinal reactions (nausea, dyspepsia, vomiting) and CNS reactions such as dizziness, insomnia and headache.[32]

9) Uses:

Nowadays, quinolones are widely used for treating a variety of infections. Quinolones are broad-spectrum antibiotics that are active against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, including mycobacteria, and anaerobes.[33]

C) Ofloxacin:

Ofloxacin is a quinolone antibiotic useful for the treatment of a number of bacterial infections.[34] When taken by mouth or injection into a vein, these include pneumonia, cellulitis, urinary tract infections, prostatitis, plague, and certain types of infectious diarrhea.[34,35] Other uses, along with other medications, include treating multidrug resistant tuberculosis.[36] An eye drop may be used for a superficial bacterial infection of the eye and an ear drop may be used for otitis media when a hole in the ear drum is present.[35]

1) Chemical Name:

(±)-9-fluoro-2,3-dihydro-3-methyl-10-(4-methyl-1-piperazinyl)-7-oxo-7H-pyrido[1,2,3-de][1,4]benzoxazine-6-carboxylic acid.[37]

2) Synonyms:[38]

Ofloxacin

Ofloxacin (French)

Ofloxacino (Spanish)

Ofloxacinum (Latin)

3) Molecular formula:

C₁₈H₂₀FN₃O₄

4) Molecular weight:

361.36

5) CAS no:

82419-36-

6) Physical appearance:

Light yellow crystalline powder.[39]

7) Solubility:

Slightly soluble in water, soluble in glacial acetate, slightly soluble or soluble in methylene chloride, slightly soluble in methanol.[39]

8) Category of Ofloxacin:

Antibiotic

9) Melting point:

250-257° C

10) Boiling point:

571-574

11) Protein binding:

32%

12) Metabolism:

Hepatic

13) Half-life:

9 hours

14) Elimination action:

8-9hrs

15) Bioavailability:

85-95% [37]

16) Structure:

Ofloxacin is an oxazinoquinolone carrying carboxyl, fluoro, methyl and 4-methylpiperazino substituents. A synthetic fluoroquinolone antibacterial agent, it inhibits the supercoiling activity of bacterial DNA gyrase, halting DNA replication. It has a role as a DNA synthesis inhibitor, an anti-infective agent and an antibacterial drug. It is an oxazinoquinoline, a N-alkylpiperazine, a N-aryl piperazine, a 3-oxo monocarboxylic acid, an organic heterotricyclic compound, a quinolone antibiotic and a fluoroquinolone antibiotic.[40]

Fig no- 5- Structure of Ofloxacin.

17) Mechanisms of Action:

Ofloxacin is a quinolone antimicrobial agent. The mechanism of action of ofloxacin and other fluoroquinolone antimicrobials involves inhibition of bacterial topoisomerase IV and DNA gyrase (both of which are type II topoisomerases), enzymes required for DNA replication, transcription, repair and recombination.[41]

18) Pharmacology:

Ofloxacin is a quinolone/fluoroquinolone antibiotic. Ofloxacin is bactericidal and its mode of action depends on blocking of bacterial DNA replication by binding itself to an enzyme called DNA gyrase, which allows the untwisting required to replicate one DNA double helix into two. Notably the drug has 100 times higher affinity for bacterial DNA gyrase than for mammalian. Ofloxacin is a broad-spectrum antibiotic that is active against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.[42]

19) Food Interactions

Limit caffeine intake.

Take with or without food. The absorption is unaffected by food.[38]

20) Storage:

In an airtight container, protected from light.[39]

21) Adverse effect: [43]

- 1) Nausea.
- 2) Diarrhea.
- 3) Constipation.
- 4) Gas.
- 5) Vomiting.
- 5) Stomach pain or cramps.
- 6) Change in ability to taste food.
- 7) Loss of appetite.
- 8) Dry mouth
- 9) Excessive tiredness
- 10) Pale skin
- 11) Pain, swelling, or itching of the vagina

22) Uses: [44]

- 1) Ofloxacin is used to treat bacterial infections of the skin, lungs, prostate, or urinary tract (bladder and kidneys).
- 2) Ofloxacin is also used to treat pelvic inflammatory disease and Chlamydia and/or gonorrhea.
- 3) Ofloxacin is used for the treatment of bacterial infections that cause:

Bronchitis

Pneumonia

Chlamydia

Gonorrhea

Skin infections

Urinary tract infections (UTIs)

23) Medical uses: [45]

Ofloxacin is used in the treatment of bacterial infections such as:

- Acute bacterial exacerbations of COPD
- Community-acquired pneumonia
- Uncomplicated skin and skin structure infections
- Nongonococcal urethritis and cervicitis
- Epididymitis
- Mixed Infections of the urethra and cervix
- Acute pelvic inflammatory disease
- Uncomplicated cystitis
- Complicated urinary tract infections
- Prostatitis
- Acute, uncomplicated urethral and cervical gonorrhea

24) Retro-synthesis of Ofloxacin:**Fig no: 6- Retro-synthesis of Ofloxacin.**

A retrosynthetic step involving the breaking of a bond to form two (or more) Retrosynthetic analysis is a technique for solving problems in the planning of organic syntheses. This is achieved by transforming a target molecule into simpler precursor structures regardless of any potential reactivity/interaction with reagents. Each precursor material is examined using the same method.[46,47].

25) Synthesis of Ofloxacin: [48]

Fig no: 7-Synthesis of Ofloxacin.

26) Synthesis of Ofloxacin Intermediate:

0.01 mole of aniline & 0.01 mole of glycerin were added in round bottom flask. Then 10ml of Conc. H₂SO₄ and was stirred vigorously. Refluxed for 1hrs and the solution was poured in cold water and was kept in freezer. Filtered at vacuum filter and recrystallized from methanol. The purity was checked by TLC with Ethyl acetate: Methanol: Ammonia (60: 40: 0.1) as a mobile phase.[49,50].

Fig no: 8- Synthesis of Ofloxacin Intermediate.

26) Characterization of impurities: [49,50,51]

The structure of synthesized intermediate was established by using various analytical methods, UV & HPLC. Hence this impurity will be further identify as intermediate in Ofloxacin. The characterization of synthesized impurity is done by following parameter:

1) Preliminary evaluation:

Molecular mass and structure using element analysis and spectral data. The odor, color and the nature of synthesized impurity was physically evaluated.

Physiochemical properties:**a) Melting point:**

The melting point of the organic compound was carried out by an open capillary in a heavy liquid paraffin bath. Melting point is a valuable criteria of purity for an organic compound as a pure crystal is having definite and sharp melting point.

b) Percentage yield:

The percentage yield of the synthesis intermediate was determined by mathematical expression.

c) Element analysis:

The element analysis of C, H, and O for synthesized intermediate was calculated in percentage and were compared to standard reference values.

2) Solubility:

The solubility of synthesized intermediate was performed in various solvents. The test were performed using 1mg/ml of compound and solvents.

27) Physiochemical properties:[48]

Table no: 4- Physicochemical property of synthesized impurity and Ofloxacin.

Sr. no	Characteristic	Synthesis Impurity			Ofloxacin		
1	Color	Light Yellowish			Light Yellowish		
2	Odor	Characteristic			Characteristic		
3	Nature	Crystalline powder			Crystalline powder		
4	Molecular formula	C ₉ H ₆ NO			C ₁₈ H ₂₀ FN ₃ O ₄		
5	Molecular weight	145.1			361.36		
6	Melting Point	204-206° C			251-254° C		
7	Element analysis	C	H	N	C	H	N
		73.4	4.76	9.70	59.83	5.2	11.6

It was observed that synthesized compound was light yellow crystalline solid with characteristic odor. The melting point was found to be 204-206° C. Elemental analysis was carried out in which the % C, H & N was found to be 73.40%, 4.76%, & 9.70% resp.

Bulk Ofloxacin was yellow crystalline solid with characteristic odor, its melting point was found to be 251-255° C. Elemental analysis was carried out in which the % of C, H, F, N, & O was found to be 59.83%, 5.58%, 5.26%, 11.63%, & 17.71% resp.

28) Solubility:**Table no: 5- Solubility of Synthesis Compound.**

Sr no	Solvents	Solubility	Part of solute soluble per part of million
1	Methanol	Very soluble	10mg in 1ml
2	Acetone	Very soluble	10mg in 1ml
3	Toluene	Soluble	10mg in 10ml
4	Hexane	Slightly Soluble	1mg in 10ml
5	Acetonitrile	Very soluble	10mg in 1ml

The solubility of synthesized compound was done in various solvents. The impurity is highly soluble in methanol, acetone & acetonitrile. And less soluble in hexane & toluene. The solubility study will be use full in further study to decide the mobile phase for TLC, HPLC & UV method development.[39]

29) Summary of Synthesis impurity:**Table no: 6 –Summary of synthesized impurity.**

Sr no	Parameter	Result
1	Structure	
2	IUPAC	Quinolin-4(1H)-one
3	Molecular Formula	C ₉ H ₆ NO
4	Molecular weight	145.1gm
5	Practical Yield	2.6gm
6	Theoretical Yield	3.70gm
7	% Yield	86%

SUMMARY:

Ofloxacin is a fluoroquinolone antibacterial antibiotic. Ofloxacin binds to and inhibits bacterial topoisomerase II (DNA gyrase) and topoisomerase IV, enzymes involved in DNA replication and repair, resulting in cell death in sensitive bacterial species. Ofloxacin is a second generation fluoroquinolone that was previously used widely for therapy of mild-to-moderate bacterial infections, but which has been replaced by more potent and less toxic fluoroquinolones and is now used largely topically as eye and ear drops. Ofloxacin has been linked to rare instances of acute hepatocellular injury. The synthesis quinolin-4(1H)-one was tested for preliminary test, physical constant, pH, TLC and element analysis as per IP. The characterization of bulk Ofloxacin drug was carried out. The element analysis was also be carried out. The nitrogen was present in impurity, while halogen were absent. Identification test were done and Ofloxacin as per IP, showed positive result. Quinolin-4(1H)-one was impurity found in Ofloxacin. This impurity is confirmed by doing various method development was performed. The above article showed the quinoline group present in the Ofloxacin & this group was found to be impurity in bulk. Thus it was found that impurity quinolin-4(1H)-one was found to be within the limit as per ICH guideline (0.1%).

CONCLUSION

This review indicates all about the quinolone antibiotic is a member of a large group of broad spectrum bacteriocidals. Nearly all quinolones antibiotics in use are fluoroquinolones, which contains a fluorine atom in their chemical structure and are effective against both gram positive & gram negative bacteria. The newly classification of Quinolone drugs is also describe in this. Ofloxacin drug was describe in this article. The Retro-synthesis of Ofloxacin & synthesis of Ofloxacin intermediate was describe above in this. The Quinolin-4(1H)-one is the intermediate synthesis was found in the Ofloxacin. Quinolin-4(1H)-one is impurity found by various method development was done with Ofloxacin. And impurity that was found to be within the limit.

ABBREVIATION:

DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
MIC	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
TLC	Thin Layer Chromatography
UV	Ultra-Violet Spectroscopy
HPLC	High Performance Liquid Chromatography

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